
ANALYSIS OF MILK PRODUCTION IN MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract:

The present paper seeks to analyze the Importance of Milk Production in India and Milk Production in Maharashtra and India. Milk is one the necessary component of human body. It enriches with protein and it provides multidimensional advantages from the point view of human health. Now day's milk production in India is steadily increasing in all the states and union territories. Maharashtra is one the biggest player in terms of milk production growth. However, the worlds second highest population lives in India and we have still vulnerable population. Therefore, India needs to be achieving highest pace in context of milk production growth. For this, technology should be used in production process and farm level. If the government use devise proper suitable dairy development policy, it will lead to enhancing milk production rapidly so that, it will also help the reduce milk deficit and nutritional problems of region and poor people.

Keywords: *Importance of Milk Production in India and Milk Production in Maharashtra and India.*

Introduction:

Since ancient era, milk is considered is major source nutrition. Milk is one of the major components of human nutrition and diet. Milk increases size growth of human body. Milk is helpful to decrease weight of human body. Milk lies vitamins minerals. It has potassium, phosphorous, antioxidants and magnesium. It leads to strong human bones. Milk is nutritious and it is much important for the growth and development of babies. Therefore, milk is understood to be a key component of human life. In India

agriculture is prime occupation especially in rural parts of the country. Similarly, milk is prime source in a majority household in India. There would be no butter, cheese, porridge, milkshake ice cream or yogurt unless the availability of milk production in our country. The supply of milk in India is made by agriculture sector because; dairy farming is being supplementary business of agriculture.

Objectives:

1. To Study the Importance of Milk Production in India.

2. Analysis of Milk Production in Maharashtra and India.

Data Base and Methodology:

The present paper is based on completely secondary data. The required and necessary data concerned Analysis of Milk Production in Maharashtra have been taken from different sources like books, articles and internet etc. Similarly, the percentage technique was used to analyze the data.

Interpretation of Data:

The present paper analyzed by using some statistical tools like average, standard deviation co-efficient of variance and compound annual average growth rate (CAGR) etc.

Results and Discussion:

Importance of Milk Production in India:

India is fastest growing economy in the world, India is largest producer of several agriculture commodities, and milk is one of the major out of all of them. India has vast population with most second largest population. Therefore, India is known as second largest consumer market across the world. India is the largest milk producer in the world with production 146 million MT. NDDB, was forecasted that Indi's milk production is

expected to grow from 146 million MT to 180 million MT up to 2020 and demand is projected to be reach 200 million MT. The Indian household dairy market is the amongst largest and fastest growing market across the world. Therefore, Indian dairy business has well potential to reach the meeting desirable growing demand of milk.

India is the biggest consumer and producer of milk accounting for 17% world's milk production and self-sufficient now. The domestic demand for milk had estimated to be growing at 4.8% in 2015, whereas supply is growing only at a lower rate. This mismatch between demand and supply of milk in India has identified worrisome. Besides, consumption of milk and dairy products in the entire developing world including India and China which have been major portion of the world's population. Milk production sector played important role to achieving food security, reducing global poverty, generating employment opportunities for women and providing a regular source of income for rural. Besides, dairy development has helped in boosting rural economic growth and empowering rural women. Similarly, 160 million children around the world receive benefits from milk through school feeding programme. Initially, in decade 1950 to 1960 India was milk deficit country and was depending on import.

During the period from 1991 to 2018, the per capita availability of milk increased from 178 (gm/day). During this period, milk production in India increased from 55.6 million tonnes to 187.7 million tonnes and growing at 4 per cent compounded annually. Now, India is self-sufficient in milk production because 73 million dairy farmers are engaged in the dairy sector especially women. According to International Farm Comparison Network, Dairy Report 2018, about 10 states in India produce 81 per cent of the milk and the rest of states and Union territories produce

the balance 19 per cent and 9 states have achieved per capita availability of milk at par with the national level.

Analysis of Milk Production in Maharashtra:

Maharashtra is progressive and developed state in India. The state has total 35 districts. In Maharashtra. The state has fully connected with co-operative dairy development. Therefore, the state is most important in terms of milk production in India.

Table. No. : Milk Production in Maharashtra

Sr. No.	Year	Milk Production (in Lakh MT)		Per Capita Availability (in Grams Per Day)	
		Maharashtra	All India	Maharashtra	All India
1	2012-13	87.34	1324.31	213	299
2	2013-14	90.89	1376.85	219	307
3	2014-15	95.42	1463.14	228	322
4	2015-16	101.52	1554.91	239	337
5	2016-17	104.02	1636.94	243	352
6	2017-18	111.02	1763.47	254	370
7	2018-19	116.55	1877.49	264	390
8	2019-20	120.24	1984.40	269	460
9	2020-21-	137.03	2099.07	305	427
	Average	105.5	1675.6	248.2	362.7
	SD	38.2	273.2	28.6	54.8
	CV	36.3	16.3	11.5	15.1
	CAGR	5.82	5.93	4.59	4.55

Source: Economic Survey of Maharashtra

The above table no. 1 depicts that the milk production in Maharashtra during the given period. The average milk production of Maharashtra was reported

105. 5 lakh MT. The compound annual growth rate of milk production of Maharashtra is reported 5.82 per cent. It is indicated that, the growth in milk

production of Maharashtra is positive during the given period of time. Due to the being help from government to dairy farmers and co-operative dairies, It has led to steady growth in milk production of Maharashtra state. The co-efficient variance of the milk production of Maharashtra recorded 36.3 percent; it shows normal variation and fluctuation during the period taken into consideration. Similarly, the average milk production of India was recorded 1675.6 lakh MT during the given period. The compound annual growth rate of milk production of All India is reported 5.93 per cent. It shows the positive trend in milk production of country. Owing to the implementation of planning and technology on the government level, the growth in milk production of All India witnessed steady but progressive trend during the given period of time. The co-efficient variance of the milk production of All India level recorded 16.3 percent, it shows small volatility and variation during the period taken into consideration. Besides, the average per capita availability of milk in Maharashtra state is reported 248.2 grams per day as compared to average world per capita availability of 229 grams per day during the given period. The compound annual growth rate of the per capita availability of milk in Maharashtra state is reported 4.59 per cent during the given

period. Due to the increasing scale of milk production in Maharashtra. This has reflected into positive but steady growth in per capita availability of milk in Maharashtra state during the given period of time. The co-efficient of variance of the per capita availability of milk in Maharashtra state is recorded 11.5 per cent, which shows lower volatility and fluctuation. And the average per capita availability of milk in All India level is registered 362.7 grams per day as compared to average world per capita availability of 229 grams per day during the given period. The compound annual growth rate of the per capita availability of milk in All India level is registered 4.55 per cent during the given period. The co-efficient of variance of the per capita availability of milk in All India level is recorded 15.1 per cent, which shows lower volatility and fluctuation during the given period. In conclusion, the milk production and per capita availability of milk in Maharashtra state is progressively increasing as increasing at All India level.

Conclusion:

Milk is one the necessary component of human body. It enriches with protein and it provides multidimensional advantages from the point view of human health. Now day's milk production in India is steadily

increasing in all the states and union territories. Maharashtra is one the biggest player in terms of milk production growth. However, the worlds second highest population lives in India and we have still vulnerable population. Therefore, India needs to be achieving highest pace in context of milk production growth. For this, technology should be used in production process and farm level. If the government use devise proper suitable dairy development policy, it will lead to enhancing milk production rapidly so that, it will also help the reduce milk deficit and nutritional problems of region and poor people.

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